

**METHODOLOGY OF USING STEAM TECHNOLOGY IN
TEACHING PHYSICS****Sh.A. Ashirov**

Associate Professor,

Gulistan State University

N.T. Imankulov

Senior Lecturer,

Gulistan State University

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STEAM education, physics methodology, interdisciplinary integration, innovative technologies, project-based learning (PBL), critical thinking, practical skills, modern lesson.

ABSTRACT

This article investigates the methodology of using STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Mathematics) technology to increase the effectiveness of teaching physics in the modern educational system. Unlike traditional teaching methods, the authors highlight the role of the STEAM approach in developing critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and creative skills in students. The article provides specific methodical recommendations and examples for ensuring interdisciplinary connections in physics classes and organizing integrated practical projects and laboratory sessions. The research results show that STEAM technology increases students' interest in the subject and serves to connect theoretical knowledge with real-life practice.

Necessary reforms are being implemented to reform the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Among these, we can highlight the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Organization of Modern Schools," the Resolution "On Measures to Further Improve the Preschool Education System in 2017-2021," and many other reforms aimed at bringing our country's educational system on par with the world's leading educational systems. To achieve these goals, STEAM technologies began to emerge in the national education system in 2016.

Today, STEAM technologies are widely recognized worldwide. In some countries, this technology has been adopted as the national educational standard. The word STEAM is an acronym formed from the first letters of four English words, where: S stands for Science, T for Technology, E for Engineering, and M for Mathematics. Recently, the letter A for Art was also added to this acronym. Emphasizing these directions, educational work under STEAM technologies is conducted by demonstrating their interconnectedness with one another.

To fully implement STEAM technologies in the educational system, generalized ideas from both theoretical and empirical research are required. An initial analysis of foreign experience in training school teachers through interdisciplinary approaches shows that their use of STEAM technologies

in teaching physics and mathematics increases work efficiency and self-esteem. Foreign research on the

practice of implementing STEAM education in schools describes a number of models for developing lessons that ensure their effectiveness. Due to its interdisciplinary nature, various specialists—including university representatives, company experts, and educational departments—participate in developing lesson materials. In each of these models, several uncertainties and disagreements arise among subject teachers.

It is worth noting that the practice of engineering school education is built on an activity-based approach through experimentation, research, design, construction, and programming. From this point of view, teachers directly involved in STEAM education raise the following questions: what is the role of their specific subject in developing comprehensive STEAM lessons? How can textbook content be linked to real-life tasks? What is the connection between research study and engineering design? Based on teachers' feedback, researchers ask themselves which collaborative activity is more effective: the one between teachers of the same subject or teachers of different subjects. Generally, all studies show positive changes in this regard.

The methodology of using STEAM technology in teaching physics in secondary schools should be implemented in various forms:

1. In studying and summarizing physical-technical material in schools, in solving and formulating problems with physical-technical content, and in performing laboratory and home experiments;
2. In practice-oriented elective courses in physics, as part of pre-vocational training in information work.

In addition to being crucial for motivation, physics education gains personal meaning by enriching its content with material of high scientific and practical importance. In a properly organized educational process, mastering modern physics problems contributes to the following:

- A significant expansion of the scope of basic physical phenomena mastered by students;
- The integration of physical knowledge;
- Ensuring the unity of the fundamental and practical components of education;
- Overcoming formalism in mastering theoretical knowledge, giving it the necessary effectiveness for practical activities;
- Mastering a wide range of methods and tools of physics research.

Indeed, a number of fundamental effects that shape the character of modern physics—but are not yet properly reflected in physics education—have been discovered within the instrumental structures of technical objects. It is enough to mention the Quantum Hall Effect, which is used to determine fundamental physical constants and establish the integer electrical resistance standard. This effect, discovered in the device structures of field-effect transistors, leads to the concept of composite particles (fractional charge quasiparticles) and manifests itself in device semiconductor heterostructures.

Thus, on one hand, mastering the physics and technology of semiconductor device structures is essential for understanding fundamental effects that expand our comprehension of the subatomic world. On the other hand, the regularities established during their study become crucial in mastering

the achievements of physics. For instance, the regularities in the behavior of two-dimensional electron systems in thin semiconductor layers, manifested in the Quantum Hall Effect, currently define promising directions—such as developing new semiconductor lasers and high-speed field-effect transistors. Consequently, quantum physics (quantum macrophysics) once again redefines the qualities of engineering science that emerged during the development of semiconductor electronics.

In the process of solving physical-technical problems, depending on the nature of their content and activity, students' independence can be formed as a systemic quality of personality manifested in a number of abilities, including:

- The ability to set goals (problems) in a specific field of activity;
- The ability to design and consistently implement a program to achieve the goal;
- The ability to demonstrate flexibility, variability of actions, and a combinational approach to their implementation;
- The ability for critical self-analysis and self-assessment;
- The ability to reasonably defend one's ideas and decisions;
- The ability to organize and participate in collective creativity.

In conclusion, we note that another important development based on studying physics problems is the personality trait of taking responsibility for decisions made, judged by the practical significance of their activity results.

Let us examine in detail the importance of forming skills to solve physics problems from the perspective of improving the most critical indicators of the educational process—its effectiveness and quality. We define the quality of the educational process as a characteristic of the pedagogical system that determines its compliance with the current and potential needs of the individual and society, as well as state requirements for training highly qualified specialists. It follows from the definition itself that students' acquisition of skills and experience in solving physics problems helps to increase (ensure) the quality of the educational process due to compliance with all requirements.

The role of educational outcome quality indicators is characterized by the breadth of experience, defined by the composition of the objects and methods of activity, as well as the level of mastering reality, and the quality and durability of knowledge. The formation of skills to solve physics problems undoubtedly contributes to the increase of all the above indicators:

- **Breadth of experience**, related to the diversity of activity objects and methods inherent in the content and process of solving physical-technical problems;
- **The level of mastering reality**, due to achieving an effective and creative level in the process of solving physical-technical problems, which is defined as the highest level in pedagogy;
- **The quality of mastering**, in acquiring the knowledge necessary to solve problems due to a high level of student independence, and using it as a guiding tool for practice-oriented activity.

The quality indicators of educational content are its completeness, scientific accuracy, and optimality. As the first two indicators increase, the level of forming physical-technical problem-solving skills increases in connection with what was stated above about its role in implementing the principle of scientific accuracy. The third indicator depends on the level achieved in implementing the principle of differentiation and individualization of the physics teaching process.

Finally, the quality indicators of educational technologies refer to their alignment with the general goals and content of education, as well as the content and methods of these specific disciplines. Their widespread use increases the level of formation of physics problem-solving skills as it approaches a real, practice-oriented educational process in cognitive-search activity. This contributes to improving technology in all its subsystems, including methods and tools for stimulating and motivating cognitive activity, managing it, and correcting the obtained results.

From the perspective of educational effectiveness, we accept the following definition: educational effectiveness is a measure of achieving educational and cognitive results during the joint activity of the student and the teacher, through the rational use of the resources of this activity and the environment in which the educational process takes place.

From what has been discussed, it follows that using STEAM technology in teaching physics in secondary schools creates the conditions for implementing key problems of physics education—namely, a systemic approach and interdisciplinary connections in education.

References:

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *On Measures to Further Improve the Preschool Education System in 2017–2021*. No. PP-2707. December 29, 2016.
2. Sharipov Sh.S. *Theory and Practice of Developing an Intellectual System of Learning*. // Monograph. – T.: Fan, 2011. – 206 p.
3. *Pedagogical Technology* / Center for the Development of Higher, Secondary Special, and Vocational Education under the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – T.: TAFAKKUR, 2009. *Pedagogical Technology: Application to the Educational Process (Model of the Science subject based on modern pedagogical technology)*. Part I / Tojiev M., Alimov A.Ya. – 135 p.